

DOCUMENTATION AND ACCOUNTING OF GOODS AT RETAIL TRADE ENTERPRISES

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Annotation: In sales organizations, the main management process is sale of goods. This article gives information about documentation and accounting of goods at retail trade enterprises

Key words: documentation, accounting of goods, management process, sale of goods, trade enterprises.

The procedure and terms for the acceptance of goods in terms of quantity and quality and documentation are regulated by supply contracts, specifications, instructions on the procedure for acceptance of goods according to quantity, quality and completeness.

The supply agreement is one of the types of purchase and sale agreement, regulating relations between organizations engaged in production and wholesale trade of raw materials, materials, components, equipment.

A supply contract is a document of sale and purchase according to which the seller undertakes to transfer to the buyer the goods produced or purchased goods for the implementation of business activities.

Acceptance of goods by quantity includes verification of compliance the actual availability of goods to the data contained in the accompanying documents, and when accepting goods in terms of quality and completeness - the requirements set out in the contract. The procedure for receiving goods and its documentation depends on: the place of acceptance (in the warehouse supplier, from the transport organization, at the buyer's warehouse), nature acceptance (in terms of quantity, quality, completeness), degree of compliance actually received goods, the terms of the contract and the accompanying documents, the presence or absence of accompanying documents, etc.

If the responsible person receives the goods in the warehouse supplier, the necessary document is a power of attorney, special document, which is designed to confirm the rights and duties of the parties. The main purpose of a power of attorney is to confirm the authority of a trustee to a third party. The act necessarily fixes the rights and obligations that the fiduciary. Clearly defined rights and obligations avoid twenty illegal actions on the part of the employee for whom this power of attorney.

When accepting goods in terms of quantity, quality and completeness the conformity of the product to its characteristics is checked. Upon detection, discrepancies are drawn up acts.

The main type of disposal of goods in retail enterprises is their selling to the public mainly for cash. In a retail trade network, the release (sale) of goods to the population issued by the issuance of a check of cash registers and reflection revenue per day in the book of the cashier - teller.

If a retail trade organization keeps records of goods by sales price using the trade margin, then when accepting the goods for accounting the retailer must issue a special primary document, used in retail - a register of retail prices.

In accounting, organizations that sell retail can take into account purchased goods at their selling price (retail price), which is determined by adding the trade margin to the purchase price of goods.

Trade margin for each item of goods as a percentage of the organization sets the cost of their acquisition at its discretion. Goods that were sold during the month are written off at sale value. At the end of the month, the realized trade margin - gross profit from sales, for this, revenue is multiplied on the average mark-up percentage.

In trading organizations, one of the functions of accounting is - function of control of commodity purchases and sales.

This feature is implemented in three types: preliminary control - carried out before the start of economic operations to predict its future outcome; current control - carried out at the time of the business transaction and ensures its implementation with the greatest effect; follow-up control

- carried out after the completion of a business transaction and allows you to analyse the result obtained and predict subsequent events.

The overall purpose of internal sales control is to assess whether are presented fairly objectively in accordance with generally accepted accounting standards for accounting entries, and the general the effectiveness of the control and management functions of a trade organization, related to this process.

Internal control is necessary in order to timely have information about deviations that have arisen in the organization, exceeding the allowable scale.

Internal control is observation, examination and (or) verification compliance of the processes of functioning of the object of control with the laws, standards, plans, norms, rules, orders, other accepted management decisions. By identifying deviations and establishing their causes occurrence, control allows you to quickly develop and implement on practice activities aimed at optimal functioning tested object, increasing the efficiency of its work.

The procedure for controlling commodity operations in organizations engaged in trade activity is to monitor, inspect and verify compliance of the organization's functioning processes with laws and standards, plans and norms, rules and orders, as well as other accepted management decisions. By identifying deviations and establishing their cause's occurrence, control allows you to quickly develop and implement measures that will improve the efficiency of the organization in the future.

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